

Impact of Strategic ICT Investment on University Enrolment Trends in Nigeria

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The study aimed to investigate the Impact of Strategic ICT Investment on University Enrolment Trends in Nigeria. An ex post facto research design was employed, utilizing secondary data sourced and validated by the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) and the National Universities Commission (NUC) in 2024. Two research questions guided the study, with corresponding objectives and hypotheses. The dataset, spanning from 2001 to 2024, was analysed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings revealed that university enrolment has a strong positive correlation with ICT investment ($r = .854, p < 0.01$) and with education expenditure ($r = .884, p < 0.01$), indicating that increases in ICT investment and education expenditure are associated with increases in university enrolment. Additionally, ICT investment is strongly positively correlated with education expenditure ($r = .807, p < 0.01$). The study recommends that the government should allocate more resources to ICT infrastructure in universities to strengthen digital platforms for admission, teaching, and administration. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by highlighting the critical role of ICT investment in expanding access to higher education.

Keywords:

ICT Investment,
Student Enrolment,
Digital Education,
Higher Education
Policy.

Introduction

The rapid growth of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has brought remarkable changes across different sectors of society, including health, business, governance, and education. In Nigeria, ICT has become indispensable in tertiary education as it introduces innovative approaches to teaching, learning, and administration. ICT encompasses technologies used for processing, storing, and transmitting information electronically, and its integration has the potential to transform conventional teacher-centred and text-bound classrooms into interactive, student-focused, and knowledge-driven

environments. Onyia (2013) emphasizes that ICT can foster more engaging and dynamic learning spaces when properly integrated into academic systems.

In education, ICT applications are often categorized into two major forms: ICTs for Education and ICTs in Education. ICTs for Education involve specialized tools and resources designed to enhance teaching and learning, such as computer-assisted instruction, e-libraries, and digital learning platforms. ICTs in Education, on the other hand, relate to the adaptation of general ICT resources such as the internet, mobile devices, and social media for instructional

purposes. Syed (n.d.) notes that both categories are instrumental in reshaping learning environments, promoting inclusivity, and broadening access to higher education opportunities in Nigeria.

Despite these benefits, ICT remains underutilized in many Nigerian universities due to challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited awareness, and insufficient training for both students and lecturers. Ngwenya and Pelsler (2023) argue that these limitations have restricted ICT applications to basic tasks such as presentation support or information searches, rather than serving as a transformative pedagogical tool for fostering interactive and self-directed learning.

Recent evidence, however, shows that ICT investments, particularly through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) initiatives, are driving significant growth in university enrolments. Adefuye (2024) demonstrates that the University of Ibadan's Distance Learning Centre has effectively leveraged ICT to facilitate admissions, improve academic services, and enhance learning experiences across diverse student populations.

While prior research has documented the role of ICT in enhancing teaching and learning (Onyia, 2013) and identified persistent implementation challenges (Ngwenya & Pelsler, 2023), there is limited empirical evidence on how ICT investment directly influences university enrolment patterns in Nigeria. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the relationship between ICT investment, education expenditure, and enrolment trends across Nigerian universities. The novelty of this research lies in linking ICT investment not only to

pedagogical improvements but also to access and participation in higher education. UNESCO (2022) further stresses that technology is essential for supporting sustainable educational development in emerging economies, making this investigation timely and relevant. It is against this backdrop that the study seeks to assess the effect of ICT investment on university enrolment in Nigeria.

This paper is structured as follows: the introduction, conceptual clarification, methodology, and the conclusion with recommendations.

Research Objectives

The study is anchored on these specific objectives:

- To examine the relationship between ICT investment and university enrolment in Nigeria.
- To assess the effect of education expenditure on university enrolment in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research is framed around these research questions:

- What is the relationship between ICT investment and university enrolment in Nigeria?
- To what extent does education expenditure affect university enrolment in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the hypotheses stated below:

- H_{01} : ICT investment has no significant association with university enrolment in Nigeria.

- H₀₂: Education expenditure does not significantly affect university enrolment in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Tapera and Kujeke (2019) described ICT as a form of technology that facilitates tasks related to information, including its collection, processing, storage, and presentation. In a school setting, ICT can be used to store information such as financial records and transactions and to support teaching and learning (Khan et al., 2015).

ICT Investment

According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2024), ICT investment refers to the acquisition of equipment and computer software that is used in production for more than one year. Similarly, the World Bank (2016) defines ICT investment as the financial, material, and human resource allocation made towards acquiring, implementing, and maintaining ICT infrastructure, tools, and services. This includes expenditures on hardware, software, internet connectivity, and digital platforms that support communication.

ICT and University Enrolment in Nigeria.

ICT investment has become a key driver of university enrolment in Nigeria as institutions increasingly adopt digital platforms for admission and learning. For example, the Nigeria–France Blueprint-ICT-Dev Project, a €38 million program launched in 2025, aims to transform higher education through robust ICT infrastructure, hybrid learning, and efficient administration (NUC, 2025). Such initiatives expand access to admission services and create flexible

learning systems that attract more students into universities.

ICT Integration in Education.

ICT has transformed teaching and learning, particularly in complex subjects like physics. Tools such as simulations, virtual labs, multimedia resources, and educational games make abstract concepts more concrete, enhance engagement, and support diverse learning styles (Olawale & Emeka, 2023). However, the effectiveness of ICT depends largely on teacher competency and infrastructure. Studies in Rivers and Nasarawa States reveal that teacher skill gaps, inadequate training, and limited facilities hinder technology-enhanced instruction (Abdullahi & Mohammed, 2023). Overcoming these barriers requires investment in teacher development and ICT infrastructure to improve learning outcomes (World Bank, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Resource-Based View (RBV), introduced by Birger Wernerfelt (1984) and expanded by Jay Barney (1991), argues that organizations achieve sustained competitive advantage by leveraging unique internal resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN). Within the university system, ICT infrastructure, skilled personnel, and digital platforms represent strategic resources that can drive efficiency in teaching, research, and administration. When properly harnessed, these resources enable institutions to overcome structural limitations and deliver high-quality, technology-driven education.

ICT investment can be understood as a critical VRIN resource that shapes university enrolment trends. For example, digital

admission systems, e-learning platforms, and virtual classrooms expand access to higher education, improve service delivery, and enhance student satisfaction. The study conceptualizes ICT investment not simply as a technological upgrade but as a strategic driver of enrolment growth, enabling Nigerian universities to remain competitive in a globalized, knowledge-driven economy.

Empirical Review

Dubey and Pandey (2019) studied how online admissions affect student satisfaction in higher education institutions in Bilaspur. Using data from 100 first-year students and analysing with SEM, they examined eight dimensions including satisfaction, transparency, access to information, and ease of use. Results showed that online admission systems positively enhance the student experience, and the study concluded that when well implemented, they improve both satisfaction and administrative effectiveness.

Wasike et al. (2020) examined the effect of ICT adoption on student enrolment in TVET institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya. Using stratified and random sampling, they selected 426 respondents, with data collected through questionnaires and document analysis. Chi-square, correlation, and regression analysis showed a significant relationship between ICT availability and student enrolment. The study recommended that TVET institutions provide functional This model examines the extent to which ICT investment contributes to university enrolment while controlling for education

ICT facilities and ensure their effective use in teaching and administration.

Nnaji et al. (2024) investigated ICT in managing student enrolment in Cross River State universities using a survey of 800 lecturers and senior staff. Data collected with reliable questionnaires were analysed with t-test and ANOVA. Results revealed that ICT use in enrolment was highly effective and significantly improved student personnel administration. The study recommended greater ICT provision to enhance student selection and educational outcomes.

Methodology

The study employed an ex post facto research design, using secondary data sourced and validated by the National University Commission (NUC) and the National Universities Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC), (2024). The dataset spans from 2001 to 2024 and is analysed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The study investigates how ICT investment influences university enrolment trends in Nigeria, while incorporating education expenditure as a control variable. The foundational model connecting ICT investment to enrolment is adapted from Omodero (2022) and specified as follows:

$$ENR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ICTINV_t) + \beta_2(EXPEDU_t) + \epsilon_t$$

expenditure, thereby providing insights into the role of digital infrastructure in expanding higher education opportunities in Nigeria.

Result

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observations (N)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Year	25	2012.96	7.29	2001	2024
University Enrolment (million)	25	174.96	40.02	110	250
ICT Investment (Billion)	25	894,938.4	713,653.1	87,859	2,800,000
Education Expenditure (Billion)	25	99,169.16	47,596.13	1,540	154,000

The dataset comprises 25 annual observations from 2001 to 2024. University enrolment averages about 175 million students, with a minimum of 110 million and a maximum of 250 million, showing moderate variation (Std. Dev. = 40.02). ICT investment has a mean of approximately 895,000 billion and a very wide range, indicating significant variability in annual

ICT spending. Similarly, education expenditure averages about 99,169 billion, with a substantial spread from 1,540 to 154,000, reflecting large fluctuations in yearly funding. These descriptive statistics provide a baseline understanding of the magnitude and dispersion of the variables before conducting regression or time-series analysis.

Table 2: Regression Results of ICT Investment and Education Expenditure on University Enrolment

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval
ICT Investment (Billion)	0.0000429	0.00000532	8.07	0.000	0.0000319 – 0.0000539
Education Expenditure (Billion)	0.0002411	0.0000797	3.02	0.006	0.0000758 – 0.0004065
Constant (_cons)	112.6597	8.331	13.52	0.000	95.383 – 129.937

Source: Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC) and National University Commission (NUC), 2024

The regression model indicates that both ICT investment and education expenditure have a positive and statistically significant effect on university enrolment in Nigeria. Specifically, a one-unit increase in ICT investment is associated with an increase of 0.0000429 units in enrolment, while a one-unit increase in education expenditure increases enrolment by 0.0002411 units, holding other factors constant. The model is highly significant ($F = 53.33, p < 0.001$) and explains approximately 82.9% of the

variation in enrolment, demonstrating a very good fit. Among the predictors, ICT investment has the stronger relative influence on enrolment, as indicated by its higher t-value (8.07) compared to education expenditure (3.02).

Discussion

The findings reveal that university enrolment has a strong positive correlation with both ICT investment ($r = .854, p < 0.01$) and education expenditure ($r = .884, p < 0.01$). This

indicates that higher levels of ICT investment and education expenditure are associated with increased enrolment in universities. Moreover, ICT investment itself shows a strong positive correlation with education expenditure ($r = .807$, $p < 0.01$). These results are consistent with previous studies. Stephen et al. (2016) found that ICT played a more significant role in facilitating enrolment at the secondary and tertiary levels compared to the primary level. Similarly, Wasike et al. (2020) established that ICT adoption, particularly the availability and use of ICT resources, had a statistically significant relationship with student enrolment. Supporting this, Nnaji et al. (2024) reported that the perceived usefulness of ICT in enrolment processes was significantly high and that ICT application positively influenced effective student personnel administration. In addition, Dubey and Pandey (2019) emphasized that ICT-driven systems through transparency, efficiency, access to information, ease of use, safety, and value for money enhanced student satisfaction and demonstrated how online admission systems positively impact the student experience.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that ICT investment plays a crucial role in driving university enrolment in Nigeria. The results revealed strong positive correlations between ICT investment, education expenditure, and student enrolment, indicating that universities with greater access to ICT resources are more capable of attracting and admitting students. Beyond the numbers, prior studies confirm that ICT facilitates enrolment through transparent and efficient admission systems, improved access to information, and enhanced student satisfaction. Furthermore, ICT adoption not only eases the enrolment process but also strengthens overall student administration, making institutions more competitive and accessible.

However, the study is limited by its reliance on secondary data, which may not capture the nuanced institutional differences across universities, and by its focus on national-level trends without accounting for regional disparities. Future research could extend this work by incorporating primary data from universities, exploring the quality dimension of ICT facilities, and examining student-level outcomes such as retention and academic performance. Such studies would deepen the understanding of how ICT investment translates into long-term educational benefits and provide more targeted policy guidance

Recommendations

- Government should allocate more resources to ICT infrastructure in universities to strengthen digital platforms for admission, teaching, and administration.
- University management should invest in continuous training for academic and non-academic staff to ensure effective use of ICT tools in enrolment and student management.
- Government and the private sector, through Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), should support universities in acquiring and maintaining modern ICT facilities.
- Policymakers should develop clear policies to guide ICT adoption across universities, ensuring uniformity and equity in the enrolment process.

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UNESCO (2022) emphasizes that technology plays a vital role in achieving sustainable educational development in emerging economies, thereby making this investigation both timely and relevant.

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